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ENGLISH AND FRENCH VOCABULARY AS A PRODUCT OF HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT

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The word-stock of any language may be subdivided into the sets. The elements of one are native, the elements of another are borrowed. Borrowings are modified in phonetic shape, spelling or meaning according to the standards of the recipient language. The process of interpenetration is constantly going on. One penetrated into a certain language system, a loan word is assimilated and undergoes semantic changes. The greater are the changes, the weaker is the connection of the word with its traditional use in the original language. According to the latest lexicographic data we can speak of a formation tendency of new lexical equivalents in Indo-European languages and the necessity to study them. The French language, which is the object of the study of language, consists of several varieties. The vocabulary of the language is constantly changing, to a greater or lesser extent. Changes are tracked and recorded, which allows to adequately understand modern language, which is developing as a living thing. Social changes of time, caused by changes in the structure of the socio-political system, changes in ownership and composition of active participants in communication, cause a conscious change in language norms. This is expressed primarily in the growth of variant elements of communication, a large number of new loanwords and terms, and, finally, in stylistic changes in the meaning of oral and written language, with a marked change in the domestic sphere of communication. The problem, investigated in the article, is connected with the history of penetration of foreign words, among them English, into the French language and vice versa. Everybody can witness the influence of English borrowings in one foreign language nowadays, the process of adaptation of Anglicisms. The aim of the paper is to confirm loanwords in the French language that are a result of lexical interference of two languages – two cultures – in contact. The material of the investigation is about 70 per cent of Anglicisms, picked out from the latest mass media publications in French. The scientific novelty of the research consists in the fact that Anglicisms make up a part of the French word-stock, replenish the language vocabulary

Keywords: word-stock, assimilated, borrowings, recipient language, loan word, lexicographic data, penetration, vice versa, witness the influence, Anglicism

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1. Introduction

The English language among other three thousand existing languages, large and small, is the second only to Chinese in number of speakers. It has well over 300 million native speakers, plus probably as many more handle it in pidgin fashion or as an acquired language. It enjoys the widest distribution of any language on earth, appearing in numerous countries on every continent as an official language and unofficially in many more. Over half of the world's scientific publications, books, newspapers and magazines are entirely or partly in English. At international congresses English is used more often than any other language. More than half of the world's radio and television programs on the continents are in English. By the beginning of the 14th century, the new state of linguistic affairs had been fully recognized, and long before the end of that century it had become official [1].

Several things had been happening to the English language. It had been transforming itself, despite official support and a true written standard, from Anglo-Saxon to Middle English with the loss of many of the old flexional ending (*blinda and blindon*, for example, merged into

blinde, which forecasts the modern endless *blind*). Many changes were taking place in the sound pattern. Most important, perhaps, was tremendous infiltration of French words into the vocabulary, laying the foundation for the word-stock of modern English, which is more than half Latin-Romance. A vast flood of words of extremely frequent occurrence, usually monosyllabic in form, and which most people take for granted as being “English” from the beginning of time, were assimilated from the French of the Normans. This is a list of words that includes: *please, wait, large, air, noise, play, piece, nice, poor, real, cry, catch, chase, grief, pray*, etc. [2]. Add a few two-syllable words, such as *army, money, very*, where French *armee, monnaie, vrai* have been replaced the original Anglo-Saxon here.

The intrusion of a French word into the language did not displace the old Saxon form, both lived on happily together, giving rise to rich series of synonyms (*heal-cure, lord-sire, glass-mirror, wedlock-marriage, sorrow-grief, might-power, bid-pray, doom-judgement*; in each couple the first word is Saxon, the second is French). But in case of *medicine, geometry, lieutenant, uncle*, the

French word effectively displaced the Saxon derived *luchcraft, earthcraft, steadholder*.

The complete and successful marriage of Germanic and Latin-Romance is shown by the late 14th century output, which blended both vocabulary elements into a literary language that is substantially modern English and can be understood by the present-day reader with a minimum of study and explanation.

2. Literary review

The language was to undergo many changes before achieving its modern state. First English vowel sounds were radically transformed, though little of that phonetic transformation was reflected in the spelling [3]. Old English vowels, both long and short, were the most part “pure” vowel sounds, without the diphthongal glide that characterizes our so-called “long” vowels of today: *a, e, I, o, u* are diphthongs, [4] consisting of a basic sound, preceded or followed by an *ou-* or *off-* glide, with the sole exception of *e*; the others are pronounced respectively [5]. The transformation was achieved in several distinct stages over a period of centuries.

Fluctuations in plural forms were largely levelled out in favor of the now almost universal *-s* formation (but there are survivals of earlier plural forming systems, such as *oxen, children, deer, feet, mice*) [5]. It is Mario Pei's theory that triumph of *-s* plural, which is general in English, widespread rare in German, may have been due to French influence [6]. Often the pilfering took place in English, with the coining of terms, which dropped out of the language after a brief lifespan. Sometimes classical-sounding words come into English from French and Italian. Most of these accretions are with us today, and form an important, not to say indispensable, part of our literary, scientific and even everyday vocabulary.

3. The purpose and the objective of the article

The aim of the article is to confirm loanwords in the French language are a result of lexical interference of two languages – two cultures – in contact.

To achieve the aim, the following objectives are set-up:

1. to draw the historical sketch of the English language;
2. to investigate the origin of French words;
3. to show the linguistic aspects of borrowings.

4. Materials and methods

Research methods: content analysis of scientific papers on the research topic to identify problematic issue to resolve; generalization of the existing positions of scientists on the language changes and development to identify the general attitude to the problem of borrowing and loanwords.

5. Research results and their discussion

The English language has its official beginning as the Anglo-Saxon, the language of invaders from the European mainland North Sea coast who in the fifth century began to push back the Celtic speaking Romanised Britons into the mountain fastness of Wales and Cornwall. Racially and linguistically the newcomers were a conglomerate of Angles, Saxons and Roman dia-

lects. For what concerns language, they formed a large part and then a vast family of related languages whose other branches are Celtic, Latin-Romance, Balto-Slavic, Greek, Albanian, Armenian and even languages of northern India, Pakistan and Iran.

Like all the older members of the Indo-European family, English had a rich system of cases for nouns and adjectives, special endings for separate verb forms, a sound structure, which has undergone radical transformations, and a vocabulary, which is scanty by modern standards, but adequate for the needs of Anglo-Saxon civilization at that period [6].

While it is true that less than a fourth of the present-day English vocabulary consists of words and roots of Anglo-Saxon origin, these constitute that segment of today's spoken language, which is basic – words that appear over again in the flow of spoken and written language: common connectives and adverbs, such as *and, but, if, who, that, which, when, where, here, there*; articles and prepositions such as *the, a, to, for, in, by, of, with, from*; adjectives, such as *hot, cold, great, small, good, bad*; nouns such as *bread, water, sea, land, world, heaven, hell*; verbs, such as *be, have, ask, answer, go, come*; pronouns, such as *I, me, he, she, it*. It is not rare to find that as many as 90 per cent of the words are of Anglo-Saxon origin.

The last invasion came with the Norman Conquest of 1066. The Normans had taken over French customs and the French language. When their leader, William of Normandy, wrested control of England from Harold, last of the Saxon kings, the language his followers spoke was the Norman dialect of French.

French, too, belonged to the great Indo-European family of languages, but it was of the Latin-Romance. For centuries the two languages remained apart: English was spoken by Anglo-Saxon lower classes, and French by the Norman lords, the clergy, the scholars, and the royal court. English at that time sank to an unbelievably low estate. Practically all writing was done in Latin or French. In the twelfth and thirteenth centuries there developed on English soil a flourishing literature in French [7].

In course of nearly three centuries and many wars against the French on the mainland, the upper classes were becoming convinced that their future lay in the new English possessions, not on the continent. By the middle of the thirteenth century they, too, were speaking English habitually. By the beginning of the fourteenth century, the new state of linguistic affairs was fully recognized, and long before the end of that century it had become official [1, 7]

But in the meantime several things had been happening to the English language. It had been transforming itself, despite official support and a true written standard, from Anglo-Saxon to middle English, with the loss of many of the old flexional endings (*blinda* and *blindan*, for example, merged into *blinde*, which forecasts the modern endless *blind*). Many changes were taking place in the sound pattern. Most important, perhaps, was the tremendous infiltration of French words into the vocabulary, laying the foundation for the word-stock of modern English, which is more than half Latin-Romance. A vast flood of words of extremely frequent occurrence, usually monosyllabic in form, and which most people

take for granted as being “English” from the beginning of time, were assimilated from the French or the Normans.

There have been attempts to “purify” the language of its foreign importations and restrict it to its original Anglo-Saxon. They have never been successful.

The complete and successful marriage of Germanic and Latin-Romance is shown by the late fourteenth century output of Chaucer, who blends both vocabulary elements into a literary language that is substantially modern English, and can be understood by the present-day reader with a minimum of study and explanation.

So, modern civilization is a matter of both adaptations and give-and-takes. The later process is common to all civilized languages. Though French purists issue denunciations against the French tendency to borrow and adopt English words. The speakers of English have taken from French far more than they will ever be able to repay for, they are probably the greatest word borrowers in history [1, 7].

English borrowings from French include not only the thousands of words that came in with the Normans, and which had achieved full citizenship during the time, such words as *crown, state, court, fax, office, mayor, prince, count, peasant, lesson, clerk, saint, faith, mercy, proof, fine, arrest, accuse, peace, battle, soldier, dress, robe, coat, fur, chair, closet, cellar, porch, amusement, art, beauty, color, pen, pain, joy, flower, flour, city, river, cost, safe, seem, obey, close, move, push, quit, allow, carry, remember, suppose, easy, single, sudden*. They also include later acquisitions that may or may not retain some trace of their origin in spelling or pronunciation *brunette, chauffeur, foyer, garage, dentist, syndicate, ballet, champagne*. Many are disguised by the reason of having used French as an intermediary because English speakers choose to adopt them to English schemes *cash, deposit, costume, pilot, medal, cartoon, laundry, manage, group, concert, attack, compliment, burlesque, even flue*.

Mutual influence of languages takes place due to close relations of world's nations. The influence of a foreign language is a kind of linguistic phenomenon that occurs in the history of every language. The process of interpenetration of the vocabulary in different languages since ancient times has become a common fact.

The process of borrowing is mostly connected with the appearance of new notions, which the loan words serve to express. When studying them a linguist cannot be content with establishing the source, the semantic sphere, to which the word belonged, and the circumstances of the process of borrowing.

Among possible causes of linguistic borrowing is the lack of native equivalents. The channels of borrowing at different social levels are direct contacts between speakers in border areas, contacts with foreigners within the country, official contacts, mass media and translation literature. Theoretically, all lexical elements of a language are borrowable, but in practice these are nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs, which make up the bulk of borrowings.

It is most evident, that a loanword has become assimilated in the native lexicon when it has the ability to form compounds and derivatives.

The vocabulary was a mobile aspect of the language, which enriches the language not only by means of derivation but also by means of borrowing, too.

Not all words are used permanently, some occur once or twice and are never used again.

In analyzing the adaptation of loanwords it is necessary to conclude, that in technical vocabulary the pronunciation is used in its original form. Most of the loanwords have changed their orthography and have been fully adapted.

It is obvious, that the vocabulary of English though firmly rooted in the Germanic-Latin-Romance-Greek base, is almost the most international on earth [6, 8].

Since ancient times up to the present days through economic, political and cultural relations among countries, the influence of interpenetration of the vocabulary in various languages has become the common fact.

Any significant event or discovery in one country soon becomes a merit in other countries, which involves the appearance of new words that name these discoveries or events.

In course of cooperation and communication, English words have penetrated into different languages partially or they assimilated and underwent semantic changes. Etymological studies help to trace the semantic development of words, having some common origin in different language systems and partially in Germanic languages.

Many studies of the increasing number of Anglicisms in modern state have been made during the last years.

The Romance languages descend from Latin and are called “romance” after the Latin name Roma. All Romance languages are of the same origin. It means they come of Latin but of different dialects. The Latin language penetrated into different regions and gave the particular character to the language because in one region Latin was popular, in the other it was official. Though the Latin language was exported into the provinces, which were remote from Romania, its contacts with the classical Latin became weaker. The Latin language was preserved only in the administration, education and church.

Though the roman conquest was durable, it means it took several centuries (about 400 years). It is evident, that the Latin language, imported into different regions and provinces, is not the same. But we can say that even Latin developed during this period [6, 9].

The French language belongs to the Romance languages group. This group includes also Spanish, Italian, Provençal (in the South of France). Generally about 400 million persons in the world speak Romance languages.

The romanisation of Gaule began by the conquest of the South-West (125 BC), the first was the ancient Greek colony, which became the Princia Romana. The development of commerce and the creation of new cities contributed to assimilation of the culture and the language of conquerors.

Many changes were produced in the Latin language like in French. They are phonetic, grammatical changes in their systems. The vocabulary is very sensible too, and not only because of modifications of the system, but especially because they reflect the changes in economic, social and cultural life. It means that the vocabulary developed quicker than the other branches of language. The vocabulary of the popular Latin and the classical one represents two styles and varieties of one language that is Latin. In its quality of style the common

language makes the limited choice among the words and synonymic expressions, which are represented in the classical Latin very widely. It was limited because the language of everyday use by all people of those epochs and especially in the environment of marshals and soldiers at that time was indispensable and usual for the whole Empire and all regions.

The next stage of the evolution of Latin is gallo-romance. It developed quickly and had many modifications, which contributed to the formation of a new language and received the name of French in the North and Provençal in the South. The gallo-romance contains lexical and grammatical peculiarities, which descend from that epoch, giving the explanation of the old Latin classical words in the vocabulary of gallo-romance.

For example: *cavallus* (>*cheval*), *berbices* (>*brebis*), *Gallia: Frantia* (>*France*), *ictus: colpus* (>*coup*), etc.

There are the words of Gloses de Reichenau, they both are dated in the 8th century. It is only after Pepin le Bref who received the foundation of the Carolingian dynasty and there reigned the idea of union with the Kingdom of Charlemagne (771–814) and they crowned the emperor in Rome in 800 [6, 10]. After the death of the only descendant Louis le Pieux the empire was divided into parts between the sons after the agreement of alliance and mutual assistance against the pretensions of the brother Lothaire. The South Gaule knew another historical chronology. These different provinces were under the domination of Burgondes and Wisigoths. Only in 536 the South was occupied by the Francs. It was integrated in the Empire of the Francs by Pepin le Bref (8th century) after the agreement of Verdum.

Later Provence (< *Provincia Fomana*) will make the part of Kingdom of Arles, which separated it during three centuries from the North of France.

The lexical differentiation of Romance words is made due the fact of using Latin in different provinces. The choice was among a big number of word combinations and synonymic expressions, which were used in Latin to describe the same objects. There are two areas in Romania (east and west) where the usage of different vocabularies existed to show the notion of prayers in the classical language: *rogare* “*prier*”>*rogar* (*esp.port.*), *ruga* (*rom.*); *precari*>*precare* “*supplier*”>*prier* (*fr.*) *pregare* (*it.*), *prega* (*prov.*)

There are some more examples to show the meaning or idea of the word “*bouillir*”, they used two verbs: *fervere*> *ferver* (*port.*), *hervir* (*esp.*), *fierbe* (*rom.*); *plorare*> *pleurer* (*fr.*), *florar* (*esp.*) and *plangere* (*pleurer avec “vehemence”*)> *piangere* (*it.*), *plange* (*rom.*)

The following words are especially used in every province: *femme* (*fr.*>*femina*), *mujer* (*esp.* > *muliere*), *donna* (*it.* > *domina*); *pomme* (*fr.* > *poma*), *mela* (>*mela*), *acheter* (*fr.*)<*accaptare* (*captare* “*saisir*”). The vocabulary was modified in two aspects: the loss and the changes of sense. The causes of these transformations of the quantitative and the qualitative order were not easy to reveal at once. The lexics of the gallo-romance period characterized the enrichment of the vocabulary of a new French language. The vocabularies were explained by the means of the common language. These are the examples: *spiritus=ventus*; *effundere=jactare* in modum equal.

The new words often represented borrowings. The quantity of Celtic words was very small (French counts about 300) and it was a special vocabulary with some exceptions: *benne*<*banna* (*it. benna*); *chene*< *cassanus*<*caxinus*; *darte*< *darbita*, *charrue*<*carruca*, etc. When they mean general notions, the Celtic words were replaced by Latin, for example: *grain*, *farine*, *lait*, *champ*. The process of derivation was very productive. The verbs had their suffixes *-are* (>*er*, >*ier*) and *-ire* (>*ir*): *cura-curare*, *sacer-secrare*, *servus-service*, *custos-custodire*, etc.

The verbs derived from nouns in *-i*, *-io* had the form in *-iare* (>*ier*): *breviare* (*of brebis*), *ampliare*, *acuitare*, *altiare*, *bassiare*, etc.. The suffix *-idiare*>*izare* enriched the vocabulary of church: *baptizare*, *anathematizare*, *cathecizare*, *exorcizare*, *scandalizare*. By the means of derivations gallo-romance enriched its vocabulary with some new abstract nouns: *vaduta*>*vue*, *perdita*>*perte*. The substantivation of the adjectives by the means of ellipse was frequent too: *exclusa aqua*> *ecluse*, *caseum formaticum*>*fromage*, *bestia inmena*>*jument*.

By the end of the period of feudal vocabulary, examined in the work of K. – J. Hollyman: *honor*, *fief* (<*franc fehu*), *service*, *serf villain* (9th century) *sergent*, *vassal* (<*celt. nassus*).

The transference of sense objected the sense of special usage and generalization of meaning: *collocare* “*placer*”>*coucher*; *manere* “*demeurer*”> *passer la nuit*, *habiter*; *captivus* “*captive*”>*malheureux* (later “*chetif*”); *fortuna* “*bonne ou mauvaise fortune*”> “*bonne fortune*”; *piscatus* “*pech*”> *poisson*; *stare* “*etre debout*”> *etre*; *hostis* “*ennemi*”> *armee*; *poena* “*punition*”> *peine*, etc.. [6, 10]

The process of English borrowing, which has accelerated in recent decades, is due to the fact that English is not only the language of a leading economic, political and military force, but also a tool of communication in all fields of science and technology, economics and finance, sports, etc. In addition, English is generally considered expressive and concise. A large French dictionary evaluates borrowing from English at 4–5 % of the current French lexicon. Considering the frequency of use of English, we see that most of them belong to specialized or semi-specialized areas and therefore are not used in everyday language. However, borrowing is a phenomenon that reflects not only language processes but also socio-economic realities, so it is an indicator of the position of language in a broad civilizational context.

Prospects for further research on this issue are in the observation and analysis of the process of English-French borrowing at the present stage of development of the languages, fixing new examples and supplementing existing registers of the borrowed vocabulary. Future investigations will expand on findings by mapping the outcomes of borrowings and any corresponding native terms from the Middle English period to present-day English, including narrowing and broadening, figurative and metonymic use, rates of polysemy. Consequently, I hope to be able to develop a model of lexical and semantic development in Middle English that is not based on competition as a leading idea and show that the achievement of standardization in vocabulary depended on increased technical specification, linked to borrowing history.

6. Conclusions

1. English belongs to the Indo-European family of languages and is therefore related to most other languages, spoken in Europe and western Asia from Iceland to India. The parent language, called Proto-Indo-European, was spoken about 5,000 years ago by nomads, believed to have roamed the southeast European plains. English is the only European language to employ uninflected adjectives; e.g., the tall man, the tall woman. As for verbs, if the Modern English word *ride* is compared with the corresponding words in Old English, it will be found, that English now has only 5 forms (*ride, rides, rode, riding, ridden*), whereas Old English *ridan* had 13. The vocabulary of Modern English is approximately a quarter Germanic (Old English, Scandinavian, Dutch, German) and two-thirds Italic or Romance (especially Latin, French, Spanish, Italian), with copious and increasing importations from Greek in science and technology and with considerable borrowings from more than 300 other languages. Names of many basic concepts and things come from Old English or Anglo-Saxon: *heaven and earth, love and hate, life and death, beginning and end, day and night, month and year, heat and cold, way and path, meadow and stream*. Cardinal numerals come from Old English, as do all the ordinal numerals except *second* (Old English *other*, which still retains its older meaning in “every other day”). *Second* comes from Latin *secundus* “following,” through French *second*, related to Latin *sequi* “to follow,” as in English *sequence*. From Old English come all the personal pronouns (except *they, their, and them*, which are from Scandinavian), the auxiliary verbs (except the marginal *used*, which is from French), most simple prepositions, and all conjunctions.

2. Although French is derived mainly from Latin (which accounts for about 60 % of English vocabulary either directly or via a Romance language), it also includes words from Gaulish and Germanic languages (especially Old Frankish). The French language belongs to the Romance language family, which is a group of languages that all evolved from the language of the Romans, Latin. Most of the language we call French today stem from the everyday Roman language “Vulgar Latin”.

It gradually changed and evolved into the Gallo-Romance language of the “Gaul” people whom we consider the main ancestors of the French today. Before the Romans arrived on the territory that we call France today, the people who already lived there spoke Celtic languages. Today, a few Celtic languages still exist. In North-Western France, Breton is still spoken today, and then there’s Gaelic, the Irish language, which is also Celtic. Today, the French language is changing more than ever. France’s colonial history has meant that the French people have made connections with peoples and cultures from all over the world, and those relationships (good or bad) are clearly visible today.

3. Borrowings enter the language in two ways: through oral speech (by immediate contact between people) and written speech (by indirect contact through books, etc.). Oral borrowing took place chiefly in the early periods of history, whereas in recent times, written borrowing gained importance. Words, borrowed orally, are usually short, and they undergo considerable changes in the act of adoption. Written borrowings preserve their spelling and some peculiarities of their sound form. Their adaptation is a long and laborious process. Assimilation is the process of adjusting a word to the phonetic and lexico-grammatical norms of the language. There are three main types of assimilation: phonetic, grammatical, and lexical. Phonetic assimilation is the process of adjusting the phonetic form of the borrowed word to the sound system of the recipient language. Grammatical assimilation is the conformation of a borrowed word to the morphological or grammatical standards of the receiving language. If a loan word is grammatically assimilated, it acquires (gets) English paradigms and categories. Lexical assimilations are the conformation of a borrowed word to the lexico-semantic system of the recipient language. If a loan word participates in word-building according to the rules of the English language, we can say it’s a lexical assimilated word.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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